

RESEARCH PAPER**Socio-Economic Development through Regional Organizations: A Study of the Implementation of Agenda 2063 by the African Union (AU) in Collaboration with China****¹Muhammad Amjad Raza* and ²Dr. Abdul Basit Khan**

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The African Union (AU) unveiled Agenda 2063 in 2013 which is a strategic framework that sets sights on wide-ranging growth, international collaborations and sustainable development, with a special focus on infrastructure development. While aligning the objectives of the Belt & Road Initiative (BRI) with those of Agenda 2063, China has also emerged as a key stakeholder in the economic wellbeing of the African continent. The instant study explores the evolving role and status of the AU with special reference to its collaboration with China in terms of socio-economic development of the continent by examining key areas of this partnership with respect to the implementation of Agenda 2063, the impact of these interactions on Africa's development, and the challenges and opportunities that lie ahead of the parties involved. By analysing the AU's strategies and initiatives in engaging with China, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play in this crucial partnership and the potential pathways for enhancing Africa's global standing through effective regional diplomacy and cooperation. It qualitatively analyses the official reports, statements, literature and public records and finds that the AU has proved quite influential and successful forum for the transformation of this "hopeless continent" into a hopeful region for its inhabitants, nevertheless, this vigilance and activism should be kept alive until the attainment of all the desired goals.

Keywords: Agenda 2063, Belt & Road Initiative (BRI), China-African Union (AU) Relations**Introduction**

In the contemporary age of technological advancement and globalization, the economic and socio-cultural cooperation among countries has become a *sine qua non*, as any nation cannot fulfil its needs solely. The case of China in that perspective is very interesting. Relationship with regional and international organizations is the main constituent of her foreign policy. She has been involved across various continents particularly during the 21st century whereas the density and intensity of this involvement depends upon various factors. The geographical contiguity has been quite normal factor for the mutual interaction of various states but the Chinese expansionism is extending beyond borders and continents. Her linkage through Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) was a prime example in that regard but the contemporary trends manifested in an extended interregional connectivity through BRI have surprised the modern world. Although Chinese involvement in South Asia and Central Asia has been the focus of attention for scholars working on the Chinese economic engagements but the China-AU partnership is the most interesting aspect of Chinese economic policy. China has developed a strong base in the African continent by investing billions of dollars while constructing numerous mega projects in the fields of Information Technology, Railways, Ports & Shipping, Roads and Bridges, etc. All this happened with the help of an active Chinese involvement with the AU. Amidst these interactions, the AU extended firm support for One-

China policy and vigorously opposed any external interference as regards China's domestic affairs which stance further solidified their partnership (African Union, 2011). The China's Africa Policy of 2006 underscored the vital role of regional organizations in Africa and it mainly focused on the AU. It affirmed China's commitment to assist the AU in realizing Africa's real economic potential. So far, the AU proved instrumental in channelizing Chinese investments to crucial sectors including infrastructure, agriculture, as well as technology. China's BRI is a valid example towards investments in African infrastructure which primarily include railways, highways, air and sea ports (Venkateswaran, 2023).

The case of the functioning of AU is also very interesting which deserves proper description. The African leaders and the respective governments signed the fiftieth Centennial 'Solemn Declaration' during the Golden Jubilee merriments of the AU's foundation in May 2013 in order to reiterate their assurance that Africa's new route to comprehensive and viable economic progression and growth would be supported (Tralac, n.d.). This pronouncement represented Africa's transformed allegiance to achieving the Pan-African Vision of "an integrated, prosperous and peaceful Africa, driven by its own citizens, representing a dynamic force in the international arena" which was manifested in Agenda 2063 (Gebu, 2023) which outlines the roadmap to African long-term socio-economic transformation over a 50-year period spanning from 2013 to 2063 (African Union, n.d.-a). Its basic purpose is to achieve sustainable development whose success would largely evolve on collective commitment of AU states and collaboration with external actors, notably China since the said Agenda closely aligns with objectives of BRI and provides coherent framework for cooperation between both actors (Gummi et al., 2020a). China, too, infused harmony between the development strategies suggested by the BRI and the Agenda 2063 hence introduced new projects for promoting intercontinental connectivity in 2013 (Sibiri, 2023). Following the said Agenda, China started to work out in coordination with AU and applied first ten-year implementation plan from 2014-2023 (Xinhuanet, 2021a) hence the investments in that specific period mainly focused on industrialization and economic development (Xinying, 2024). During 2019 to 2023, AU's status in China-Africa policy has further been solidified through various development initiatives. While analysing the pattern of African development, one may sense that all advancements reflected the close coordination between Agenda 2063 and the BRI (Ndzendze & Monyae, 2019a). Thus, China supports AU's Agenda 2063 and addresses the other areas of mutual concern that were not part of the policy framework of 2006. In the following pages, AU's performance in various sectors of China-Africa economic collaboration in pursuit of Agenda 2063 is analysed.

Education and Environmental Protection

The Agenda 2063 specifically stressed over education and skills development. In education realm, AU-China collaboration is exemplary which enhanced educational exchange alongside the capacity building. The Pan African University (PAU) had been established in 2011 with institutes in Kenya, Nigeria, Cameroon, Algeria, and South Africa to promote higher education, research, and innovation across African continent (Space in Africa, 2019). In 2014, the AU secured additional funding from the European Union (EU) to expand PAU programs, focusing over science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (African Union, 2014). Furthering the Agenda, China also contributed to the award of scholarships and student exchange programs with the AU for knowledge transfer and capacity building (Niu, 2013). Furthermore, the Luban Workshops and vocational training centres established with Chinese funding in several African countries aim to harness young Africans with technical skills needed for modern industries. These workshops were set up in pursuit of AU's Agenda 2063 goals particularly to improve education and youth employment. Also, the AU's involvement in the China-Africa Environmental Cooperation Centre, founded in Nairobi, Kenya, 2019, signifies its growing emphasis towards sustainable development (United Nations Environment Programme, n.d.). This weather centre aims to facilitate knowledge exchange and technical cooperation regarding environmental

protection as well as mitigation of the effects of climate change. The initiative, in fact, materialized AU's strong efforts to address the issues of climate change and promote green growth. It has been instrumental and helpful in implementing combined projects aiming to combat desertification as well as promoting renewable energy. Moreover, in the year 2022, the AU and China collaboratively launched the "Alliance for Green Infrastructure in Africa (AGIA)" in order to increase the finance for green infrastructure projects across the continent. The inauguration was held in Egypt in COP 27 (African Union, 2022).

Health Care and Response to Pandemic

During COVID-19 pandemic, the AU's coordination was quite significant in obtaining medicines and ensuring continuous supply of vaccines from China which underscores importance of coordinated efforts in addressing global health challenges (Witt, 2020). For instance, China donated approximately 200 million doses of COVID-19 vaccines to African countries through the AU, reinforcing the importance of the AU's diplomatic leverage in securing essential resources for the community (Mcallister & Daly, 2021). Moreover, Chinese President Mr. Xi Jinping pledged to deliver an additional 1 billion COVID vaccine doses to Africa at the FOCAC 8th Ministerial Conference held in 2021 and approved spending of \$10 billion for the next three years in the continent (Al Jazeera, 2021). He further stressed over the need of China-AU unity to fight against COVID-19 and emphasized over the fulfilment of the immunization gap. Xi declared that China would support the AU's ambitious target of vaccinating about sixty percent of Africans until 2022 (Spiff, 2021). To further support the AU, China donated additional 15000 COVID-19 vaccine doses to the AU Commission (AUC) for its diplomats and officials (Mission of the People's Republic of China to the African Union, 2021).

The other priority action under Agenda 2063 was the establishment of the Africa Centres for Diseases Control and Prevention (Africa CDC) which started functioning in 2017 (Nkengasong et al., 2017). During COVID-19 pandemic, the Africa CDC successfully coordinated continent's response by securing medical supplies, and easing up vaccine distribution (World Health Organization, 2020). These initiatives were in broader compatibility with Agenda 2063 to prepare continent for future health crises.

AU-China Diplomatic Relation

As regards political and diplomatic realm, the AU played a critical role in safeguarding African interests in bilateral as well as multilateral negotiations with China. The AU's diplomatic engagement crucially shaped policy dialogues as well as negotiations to ensure maximum benefits out of China-Africa partnership and their equitable distribution over the continent (Abrahamsen et al., 2023). The first session of annual AU-China Strategic Dialogue was held in Addis Ababa on November 24, 2008 (Consulate General of the People's Republic of China in San Francisco, 2008). Both sides agreed upon hosting dialogues turn by turn. During the inaugural session, China's Assistant Foreign Minister Mr. Zhai Jun and the Chairman AUC Mr. Jean Ping discussed the strategic dialogue mechanism, China-AU relations, and cooperation on pressing African issues such as the situations in Zimbabwe, Darfur, and Somalia. These dialogues meant for helping AU to address various challenges faced by the continent according to mandate of the body while fostering mutual cooperation, exemplifying the nature of the relationship.

From 2013 to 2023, various initiatives had been taken to strengthen the AU-China collaboration. On February 15, 2013, China and the AU organized another strategic dialogue, co-chaired by Mr. Yang Jiechi and AUC Chairperson Miss Nkosazana Dlamini-Zuma. Mr. Yang noted the substantial progress in China-AU relations, underscored by regular contacts and productive cooperation. He emphasized over the need for closer high-level exchanges and collaboration in various fields, including infrastructure and human resources, to elevate China-Africa relations to a new level and achieve win-win outcomes. During this dialogue,

Miss Dlamini-Zuma praised China's accomplishments and expressed gratitude for its ongoing support in peace and development in Africa. She reaffirmed the AU's commitment to enhancing cooperation with China, leveraging China's experience in long-term development planning, economic restructuring, and sustainable growth (FMPRC, 2013).

The AU Conference Centre hosted the first consultation session on human rights in April 2016. Liu Hua (Chinese Rep.) and Khabele Matlosa (AUC Rep.) co-presided the session. The dialogue focused on multilateral engagements, coordination, and technical cooperation between China and the AU. The purpose of this event was to enhance collaboration between both actors. The session ended with a commitment to establish a regular consultation mechanism that would monitor all human rights activities regularly (FMPRC, 2016a). During the same month (April 2016), Mr. Zhang Jun, a Foreign Ministry Official, visited the AU headquarters to meet the AUC Chairperson Miss Dlamini Zuma and other people. The trip focused on preparation for participation in the G20 Hangzhou Summit. The African side, with deep appreciation, acknowledged the special visit of the Chinese and wished for the success of the Hangzhou Summit. In May 2016, the Chinese Mission to the AU, led by Mr. Cheng Xufeng, and Deputy Chair AUC Mr. Erastus Mwencha, assembled in AU headquarter in Addis Ababa for an exchange of dialogue over China-AU cooperation. The bilateral collaboration in the industrial sector and the issue of construction of Africa Centres for Diseases Control and Prevention (Africa CDC) building was discussed. Mr. Mwencha praised China's support and emphasized the need to strengthen ties between China and the AU (FMPRC, 2016b). The initiative "Silencing the Guns" was taken in 2017 which was intended to end conflicts over African continent. It witnessed considerable progress towards conflict resolution and peacebuilding (UNDP, 2021) For this initiative, China provided valuable logistic support and funded the peacekeeping missions (FOCAC, 2021c).

The China-AU Strategic Dialogue (7th Round) was held between AUC Chairperson Moussa Faki and Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi in the first week of February 2018. In the session, Wang Yi stated that China viewed Africa as an indispensable and vital component of the 'shared future' destiny. The AU's role was exceptional in African unity and its integration, particularly in the context of the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC). In his view, the China-AU relationship was strategic and perpetual hence China will strengthen its engagements with the AU in all directions, particularly in capacity building and continental infrastructure development. The AUC Chairperson Faki paid gratitude to China for her unequivocal support to AU for institution building, peace, stability, and economic development (Khan, et. al., 2020). He hoped China would get closer to the AU by aligning its objective with Agenda 2063. He thanked China for opening the AU's representative office in Beijing and extending firm support in FOCAC. At the end of the dialogue both participants agreed to increase cooperation on global and regional issues (Embassy of the People's Republic of China in the Republic of Botswana, 2018).

The Sino-AU partnership has consistently relied upon a joint commitment to address critical human rights challenges through mutual efforts. The AU-China Human Rights dialogue mechanism has further deepened the cooperation between these two key players. It is important to note that the third AU-China Human Rights Dialogue in 2021 focused on the socio-political and economic cooperation between China and the AU (African Union, 2021). The fourth dialogue, held in April 2024, concentrated on building a solid foundation for economic cooperation, modern technology, and joint initiatives (African Union, 2024b). These dialogues illustrate a neo-liberalist approach followed in the AU-China relationship, fostering bilateral interactions with AU member states (Abrahamsen et al., 2023). This approach has led to the proliferation of mutual interests at various levels for both the AU and China. By using the AU as a tool against unilateralism, China aims to bring African countries together to ensure development support with no strings attached (OBE & Wallace, 2023). AU's very first continental report regarding progress in implementation of Agenda 2063 was presented in 33rd AU Summit held in Addis Ababa in February 2020. The

Chairperson of the AU Commission, Moussa Faki Mahamat stressed over an accelerated implementation of the Agenda while stating that the success of the project depended on the development of infrastructure (African Union, 2020).

AU-China Economic Cooperation

The AU has a unique approach of driving socio-economic transformation over the continent through its Agenda 2063 (African Union, n.d.-a). The body, in fact, is aware of the inevitability of promoting intra-African trade to attain collective economic development and protect the continent from external economic tremors. Regional economic integration is considered a key driving element of this process (African Union, 2012). Even though Africa's mounting population and urbanization grant considerable opportunities for internal consumption of the abundant material resources, the continent faces the challenges of uniform economic structures across its member states and a scarcity of necessary complementarities (Shelton et al., 2015). As a critical promoter of regional integration, South Africa props up the AU's scheme for economic unity. Agenda 2063, the AU's strategic framework, ascertains resolution of grave challenges in infrastructure development, including the ample transport infrastructure costs, with an appraised funding gulch of \$48.1 billion (Shelton et al., 2015). To address these challenges, the AU has started PIDA, a flagship initiative that strives to heighten the continent's infrastructure facility (Lisinge, 2020).

Article 9 of Constitutive Act of African Union (CAAU) provides for functions and powers of AU Assembly, which include determining common policies (African Union, 2001). The Assembly, composed of state heads or their accredited representatives as stipulated in Article 6, makes decisions by consensus or two-thirds majority in line with goals of Agenda 2063 reflecting collective will of AU member states. Policies approved in that manner would be implemented by the AUC. It's full membership in FOCAC turned her into a likely broker of the China-Africa dialogue. FOCAC provided a platform to AUC for coordination and institutionalization (Lammich, 2014). It intermediates between continental and regional level activities with China. China had financed the AU Peace and Security Council and other forums of regional integration in terms of development (Velthuisen, 2018). She had been effectively engaged with AU member states as well. Similarly, the FOCAC is an established partnership that has produced accurate action plans applicable to Africa and aligned with Agenda 2063 (Africa-China Reporting Project, n.d.). It also aligns the partnership with the AU's strategic goals vis-a-vis China. It is the real value that this partnership brings to Africa, as exemplified by the magnificent new AU Conference and Office Complex, which was built free of charge through a Chinese grant (Aiping & Zeng, 2018). According to different survey reports Africans have welcomed China and praised consequent mutual advantages delivered through enhanced infrastructure and trade/development partnerships as individually supportive goals aligned with those espoused by the AU (Sanny & Selormey, 2021).

AU mainly focused on infrastructure development, regional integration, industrialization, private sector-led intra-African trade, and sustainable utilization of natural resources (African Union, n.d.-b). While aligning itself with these tasks, the AUC supported and facilitated the development of policies and programs for achieving objectives that included inclusive growth and creation of jobs (African Union, 2024a), which would help to attain an accelerated progress in realizing the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) (African Union, n.d.-b). It encourages all such programs which would reduce or remove economic and social marginalization. The AU had also undertaken several support programs devised and adopted to address policies for inclusive growth to assist member states in their economic recovery (FOCAC, 2015). The body has a complete mechanism and institutional infrastructure to perform an appropriate role regarding economic integration and infrastructure development (Adeniyi et al., 2016). China, a key partner in the AU's development initiatives across the continent has successfully completed numerous joint

ventures which had resulted in further integration of the region and strengthening collaboration between the member states (Xinhuanet, 2021b).

Technological Advancement and Digital Transformation

Technological advancement is another key feature of Agenda 2063 with AU prioritizing digital transformation in partnership with China (Ndemo, 2021). The Digital Silk Road initiative was a part of China's BRI which led to Chinese investments in digital infrastructure of the African continent (Hussain et al., 2024). The establishment of African Space Agency in Cairo, Egypt, in 2019 further underlined AU's preference towards technological advancement over other dynamics of socio-economic development (African Union, 2023). As a consequence of this initiative which, obviously, was taken in collaboration with Chinese support, satellite communication throughout the AU was improved which also enhanced remote sensing capabilities (Verseckas, n.d.). Agriculture, disaster management, and environmental monitoring are potential sectors which were benefited from the said initiative. Moreover, the Agenda 2063 clearly articulates Africa's long-term strategy for attaining sustainable development and economic growth, enunciating various goals relating to digital connectivity (African Union Commission, 2015). The most directly related goal of the said Agenda was Aspiration 2 which envisaged for an "Integrated Continent, Politically United, and Based on the Ideals of Pan-Africanism and the Vision of Africa's Renaissance (African Union, n.d.-c)". Both actors realized this aspiration by providing a digital base to the African economy and equipping the society with digital knowledge which is now fully functional and operational hence ensuring an enhanced digital connectivity across the continent (Ndzendze & Monyae, 2019b). African countries are increasingly engaged in digital cooperation under the umbrella of the AU. So far, 52 out of the 55 AU members have signed an MoU with China on BRI (Eguegu, 2022). These member states had extensively adopted the AU's Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa which is based upon many other existing and relevant frameworks (Ayodele, 2021). China had been actively engaged with AU in digital advancements to keep itself aligned with Agenda 2063. Indeed, most African countries have joined BRI as well, and in 2015, the AU and China published a joint declaration referring to matters like strengthening cooperation in technology transfer (Eguegu, 2022). The services of Chinese telecom giant Huawei are quite important in improving the Information and Communication Technology structure of the AU.

Agriculture and Food Security

In agenda 2063, agriculture and food security are central to Comprehensive Africa Agriculture Development Programme (CAADP) (Mkomwa et al., 2022) which aims to increase agricultural productivity at least 6% annually, poverty reduction and increasing food security (CAADP, n.d.). The CAADP is a flagship programme of the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD), which ensures fast-tracking Africa's growth in agricultural sector. One of the priority areas of action under CAADP is reducing food insecurity across the continent (Bogale, 2023). It would quite largely be instrumental in pushing forward the goals and objectives of agricultural development and food security in Africa. The most crucial pool-fund investment channelled by China into African agricultural projects was the China-Africa Development Fund (Shikwati, 2012). China provided concessional loans and grants to African countries for mega agricultural projects (The State Council The People's Republic of China, 2024). Through the FOCAC summits, China has committed multifaceted support for African agriculture. Besides financial support, China invested in capacity-building programs, where African professionals were trained in modern farming techniques and technologies (Tugendhat & Alemu, 2016). China also promoted public-private partnerships to foster agricultural development in Africa, therefore, many Chinese companies operated in Africa, usually with financial support from the Chinese government, in cooperation with African governments and local businesses, to carry out large-scale agricultural projects (Jiabao & Chang, 2011; Sun, 2011).

China's assistance has been instrumental in pushing the agricultural objectives of Agenda 2063. In Africa, the Agriculture Technology Demonstration Centres (ATDCs) built by China remained the actual recipients of Chinese aid in the field of agriculture. China has had massive involvement in African agriculture since 2016. It has constructed 221 agricultural projects & farms, 23-ATDCs (until 2018) for irrigation and water conservation, 442 infrastructure projects and 622 public facilities (Nalwimba et al., 2019). Thus, the Chinese government aid to AU in the field of agriculture presented a one-of-a-kind diplomatic tool. Both China and the AU have teamed up their efforts toward the path of agricultural transformation as enshrined in Agenda 2063.

Environmental Sustainability and Climate Change

The partnership on environmental sustainability and climate change is also aligned with the objectives of Agenda 2063; the Goal 7 focuses solely on dealing with natural resources and ecosystems (United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, n.d.). Also, the environmental sustainability remained a key focus at almost every FOCAC meeting. At the Johannesburg Summit of 2015, China committed to cooperate over 10 programs charted for green development (FOCAC, 2015). Moreover, ecological protection was once again committed by China during the 2018 Beijing Summit (Tralac, 2018). China's initiatives for the establishment of the China-Africa Environmental Cooperation Centre in 2019 and several reforestation and conservation projects have consolidated the environment-management capabilities of African nation-states, ensuring, in turn, the sustainable use of natural resources as outlined by Agenda 2063 (Weidong, 2020).

It would be pertinent to recall that, while emphasizing over the need for continued collaboration regarding climate change issues, China and the AUC had signed a \$14 million grant agreement for economic and technical cooperation in 2010 (IISD, 2010). The Johannesburg Action Plan (2016-2018), adopted at the sixth FOCAC Ministerial Conference in 2015, was specifically designed to address the issues related to environmental change and climate protection (FOCAC, 2015). Leaders from China and Africa also decided to establish the China-Africa Environmental Cooperation Centre to elevate their relationship. Later, on the 5th of December 2017, the third session of the United Nations Environment Assembly was convened in Nairobi (UN Environment Programme, n.d.). In this event, China, Kenya, and the United Nations Environment Programme signed a Letter of Intent to collaborate in establishing the said Centre. Consequently, an Interim Secretariat was established on the 17th of August 2018 at the United Nations Environment Programme in Nairobi while aiming at supporting and facilitating the creation of a permanent Secretariat (UN Environment Programme, n.d.).

At the end of the FOCAC session in December 2021, the “Declaration on China-Africa Cooperation on Combating Climate Change” was issued (FOCAC, 2021b). The Heads of Delegations from China, fifty-three African countries, and the AUC recognized climate change and its negative impacts as an urgent global challenge. Both actors stressed over the urgent need to jointly deal with climate change for the future of humanity. The AU praised the measures taken by China and announced for China-Africa strategic partnership for combating climate change in the new era. Both sides agreed to convene a high-level climate change forum and further deepen the cooperation, including a proposed three-year China-Africa action plan. China committed to support Africa in implementing the Great Green Wall Initiative (WWF, 2021) and enhancing technological cooperation in disaster prevention, climate adaptation, and related fields using the following advanced systems:

1. China High-resolution Earth Observation System
2. Bei Dou Navigation Satellite System
3. Feng Yun Meteorological Satellite

China launched over a hundred clean energy and green development projects under the FOCAC, endorsed by the AU. Subsequently, both sides agreed to establish a Green Climate Fund (GCF) and implement the Green Envoy Program to further their commitment to environmental sustainability (FOCAC, 2021b).

The African Continental Free Trade Area

The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) might be termed as one of the most ambitious projects under the AU's Agenda 2063 which aims to create a single market for goods and services across all 55 AU member states (East African Community, n.d.). China's strategic partnership with Africa, particularly through AfCFTA, has been pivotal in fostering economic integration and enhancing trade relations. The AfCFTA agreement, signed by 44 AU member states in Kigali, Rwanda, in March 2018, and launched on January 1, 2021, seeks to eliminate tariffs on 90% of goods, reduce barriers over trade and services, and foster the free movement of people and investments across the continent (International Institute for Sustainable Development, 2018). The United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA) predicted that the implementation of AfCFTA would boost intra-African trade by almost 52% until 2022 (Witschge, 2018).

China's involvement in AfCFTA has been multifaceted, encompassing financial investments, infrastructure development, and technical support (Calabrese, 2021). In 2018, during the Beijing Summit of the Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC), Chinese President Xi Jinping announced a \$60 billion package for Africa, which, *inter alia*, included support for implementation of AfCFTA. This package comprised \$15 billion in grants, interest-free loans, and concessional loans, \$20 billion in credit lines, \$10 billion for a special fund for development financing, and \$5 billion for a special fund for financing imports from Africa (Benabdallah & Robertson, 2018). One of the critical components of China's support for AfCFTA has been the infrastructure development, a prerequisite for successful trade integration. China's BRI has provided for heavy investments in African infrastructure projects that aligned with AfCFTA's objectives. For instance, the Addis Ababa-Djibouti Railway, completed in 2016 with an investment of \$4 billion, has significantly reduced transportation costs and transit times, facilitating trade between Ethiopia and Djibouti (Xuanmin, 2022). This railway is a key part of the broader East African Railway Master Plan, which aimed to enhance connectivity across the region. Moreover, recognizing the growing importance of digital trade, China has supported Africa's digital transformation through initiatives such as the Digital Silk Road (Agbebi, 2022). China has also provided technical and capacity-building support to AU to ensure the effective implementation of AfCFTA. In 2019, the China-Africa Institute was established in Beijing to facilitate research and training regarding China-Africa cooperation, including trade integration under AfCFTA (FMPRC, 2019). The institute offers training programs for African officials and scholars, focusing on trade policy, economic development, and infrastructure planning.

In October 2021, in a virtual ceremony, an MoU was signed between Secretary-General of the AfCFTA Secretariat, Mr. Wamkele Mene and Chinese Vice-Minister of Commerce Mr. Qian Keming to establish an expert group on economic co-operation (Opali, 2021). The objectives of the expert group were to focus on areas such as property rights, trade and policies, as well as monitoring the progress of AfCFTA's institutional capacity and implementation. Meanwhile, Mr. Mene also highlighted the spirit of China-AU co-operation and the joint desire to create a strategic Africa-China partnership grounded on shared growth through group efforts and exchange of ideas (FOCAC, 2021a). He added that the China's noteworthy progress is in the knowledge economy, where invention motivates economic growth and intellectual property acts as its basis (BusinessGhana, 2021). He also stated that China would support AfCFTA in these essential areas. The Chinese Vice-Minister of Commerce Mr. Qian Keming revealed that China had been providing financial assistance to the AfCFTA Secretariat since its establishment, and had supported over intellectual property rights, investment, competition policy, and digital trade (Donkor, 2021). He also

highlighted that the AfCFTA would create new trading and investment opportunities for China across various economic sectors, including agro-processing, automotive, and financial technology. In his virtual address, Mr. Qian emphasized that the MoU would strengthen relations between China and Africa for mutual benefit and affirmed China's commitment to achieving this goal. Moving further, China reaffirmed its commitment to support AfCFTA during the 8th Ministerial Conference of FOCAC held in Dakar, Senegal, in December 2021. The conference, attended by high-level delegations from 53 African countries along with those of China, resulted in the declaration of Dakar Action Plan (2022-2024), which outlined some concrete measures for enhancing China-Africa trade and investment cooperation (FOCAC, 2021d).

In August 2023, President Xi Jinping participated in the China-Africa Leaders' Dialogue in South Africa which was co-chaired by South-African President Cyril Ramaphosa. During his keynote speech, Xi drew attention to the considerable progress which African nations had made over the past sixty years with an ambition of Pan-Africanism, especially in their tremendous quest for freedom, integration, and unity. He highly praised Africans for their spirit in favour of multilateralism. Xi also noticed the continuous advancement of the AU in pursuit of its Agenda 2063. He also stressed over China's support for African integration agencies such as the AfCFTA Secretariat and the Pan-African Payment and Settlement System (FMPRC, 2023).

The Role of China in Advancing Agenda 2063

Section 63 of Agenda 2063 provides that partnerships will be rationalized to enhance the benefits of Africa's transformation and integration efforts (Viswanathan, 2018). Consequently, Africa's development partners would have to align their initiatives with the inclusive framework of Agenda 2063. China has proactively responded to this mandate, as reflected in its 2015 China-Africa policy paper (China Daily, 2015). China's commitment to Africa actually operates at bilateral, sub-regional, and continental levels whereas the African nations appreciate China's development cooperation approach (Selormey & Sanny, 2021), which diverges from the traditional donor-recipient paradigm applied by the West. Instead, China focuses on partnerships based on equality and mutual benefit, adhering to fundamental values such as non-conditionality, non-interference, and respect for state sovereignty (SCIO The People's Republic of China, 2021). These principles align with the AU Constitutive Act and Agenda 2063. To operationalize this commitment, China revised its 2015 China-Africa policy paper to align its partnership schemes with the Agenda 2063 roadmap (Xinhuanet, 2021b). When the AU adopted the said Agenda to guide the continent's transformation (African Union Commission, 2015), China explicitly expressed its desire to support this vision through the said policy paper. China identified specific objectives within Agenda 2063 to support and assisted AU member states in implementing these goals (Carslake, 2024). This strategic alignment allows China to leverage its partnership with the AU to secure contracts and support developmental aims that align with Agenda 2063, coordinated by the AU for the entire continent (African Union, 2015).

As mentioned above, in addition to its policy commitments, China signed an agreement with the AU to work collaboratively on Agenda 2063 objectives, such as infrastructure development (Gummi et al., 2020a). This partnership actually exemplifies a socially constructed relationship, where both parties benefit from mutual interests. The AU uses its relationship with China to advance its multilateral agenda, while China leverages this partnership to fulfil its bilateral interests with AU member states. China's role in peace and security of the AU member states has been expanded. She contributed to the strengthening of the African Standby Force (Debelo, 2016). Regular political dialogues between China and the AU ensure enhanced international roles for both parties. The constructive nature of the AU-China relationship is evident through the lens of liberal institutionalism and regional integration. These theories postulate that human relationships are founded on shared ideas rather than material influences. The characteristics, traits as

well as partner's interests are also shaped by these ideas. Analysing AU-China relations in the context of Agenda 2063 and 2015 China-Africa foreign policy paper exposes that their collaboration is based on shared visions and objectives as presented in said documents (Ndzendze & Monyae, 2019c).

China's role in advancing Agenda-2063 is very significant as the BRI is closely aligned with the said Agenda which actually shored up Africa's development goals. This Agenda is a long-term framework striving to transform Africa into a global powerhouse through projects such as remodelling infrastructure and forming the AfCFTA (Sibiri, 2023). The BRI, on the other hand, offers Africa significant opportunities, such as launching world-class infrastructure to accelerate integration and growth until 2063. Over the past 10 years, Chinese firms have made substantial inputs towards Africa's infrastructure development, including construction of railways, ports, and power provisions, contributing to advancing continental development goals. Also, the BRI has expressively boosted economic and trade relations, with China turning out to be one of Africa's topmost investors and trade partners (Venkateswaran, 2023).

China-AU ties have experienced immense growth since signing of the MoU of 2015. This connexion is part of a wider strategy to back African development affiliated with schemes like the BRI. Various African-worthy projects, such as roads and railways, ports and industrial economic zones, have been constructed with Chinese financial help, shaping a new phase in continental infrastructure growth. Key paragons comprised the Djibouti-Ethiopia integrated railway, the Mombasa-Nairobi SGR, and the cutting-edge Kribi Industrial Port Complex in Cameroon (Gummi et al., 2020b).

Conclusion

Aristotle's notion of "unity in diversity" has quite successfully been manifested in the constitution and functioning of AU which has been emanated as successor to the Organization of African Unity (1963-1999) aspiring prosperity of the the African continent through socio-economic development. Besides, the body has emerged as a crucial player in forging Africa's foreign relations particularly with China whose involvement in African affairs and economy has already been intensified by remarkable investments in multifarious sectors. It is, in fact, extremely difficult for any organization to work smoothly while having such a large number of member states, pursuing complex activities to achieve the unanimously desired goals. It might be safely observed that the success of the AU actually lies in following the consensus-driven policies mutually agreed upon by the member states and their uniform implementation across the continent. The AU's national and regional efforts in pursuit of objectives of Agenda 2063 signify it as a unifying and coordinating body, essential for socio-economic transformation of the region. As detailed in the preceding pages, the Agenda 2063 aims to achieve multidimensional progress requiring focus on infrastructure as well as economic development while reforming sectors like health, education, environment, trade, ports, railways, bridges, etc. which, in turn, require huge financial investments and human capital for their completion. China's BRI has proved a blessing in disguise for progress of the African continent and the success of AU. Although, China is working with different countries through different regional and interregional organizations and it, sometimes, prefers to interact at state level as well (in the case of Pakistan) but the most notable involvement of China is with the AU which is successful so far because of the organizational structure and professional approach of the AU otherwise it was difficult to achieve the targets outlined by the Agenda 2063. In sum, the AU continues to drive Africa towards prosperity and progress by ensuring the speedy and transparent implementation of several mega developmental projects in all the fields particularly with the help of China.

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